

**METHODOLOGY OF DIGITALIZING THE INDEPENDENT LEARNING
PROCESS IN PREPARING SPEECH THERAPY STUDENTS FOR
INCLUSIVE ACTIVITIES**

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Abstract. Depending on the severity of the speech disorder, school-age children receive various types of speech therapy assistance. Children with mild speech disorders are admitted to public schools and can be treated in school speech therapy centers. The task of speech therapy centers is to correct disorders in the development of oral and written speech of students, to timely prevent and eliminate difficulties in mastering the general education program of students, and to conduct educational work with teachers and parents on issues of speech disorders.

The article highlights the issues of digitizing the independent learning process in preparing speech therapy students for inclusive activities.

Keywords: Digitalization, inclusive education, skills, environment, discourse, model.

The main part. The function of speech is one of the important mental functions of a person. In the process of speech development, higher forms of cognitive activity, thinking abilities are formed. The meaning of the word is in itself generalizing and in this regard reflects not only the unity of speech, but also the unity of thinking. They are not exactly similar and arise to a certain extent independently of each other. However, in the process of the child's mental development, a complex, qualitatively new unity of speech thinking, speech thinking activity, arises.

In Uzbekistan, issues of educational technologies, digitalization, and the organization of an independent learning process are reflected in the scientific and methodological works of R. Djuraev [5], N. Sayidahmedov [10], A.H.

Makhmudov, F.U. Anarbaeva [9], etc.

In the psychological and pedagogical literature, special attention is paid to the study of a person's readiness to perform a particular activity, from readiness for school to life and professional self-realization. B.G. Ananov [1] and others studied the problem of developing readiness for any activity, Ye.A. Yekzhanova, Ye.A. Strebeleva [7] and others studied the issues of developing teachers' readiness to work in the field of inclusive education.

VASlastenin defined readiness as a complex synthesis of closely related components and identifies the following:

a) psychological preparation, that is, formed (at various levels) attention to pedagogical activity, installation and work in an educational institution;

b) scientific and theoretical preparation, that is, the presence of the necessary amount of pedagogical, psychological, and social knowledge necessary for qualified pedagogical activity;

c) practical training, that is, the presence of professional skills and qualifications formed at the required level;

d) psychophysical preparation, that is, the presence of appropriate conditions for mastering teaching activities, developed personal qualities of professional significance;

e) physical fitness, i.e. health status, physical development in accordance with the requirements of pedagogical activity and professional activity, etc. [11].

Method. The problem of joint education of children without mental and physical disabilities and children with disabilities was considered at the beginning of the 20th century by the psychologist and defectologist T.A. Lasova [4] and others.

Thus, the following contradictions stand out in the area of digitalization of the independent learning process in preparing speech therapy students for inclusive activities:

- the objective need to improve the professional skills of specialists required in pedagogical activities in an inclusive educational environment and the lack of adapted models for implementing this strategic task in the practical activities of a speech therapist in an inclusive educational environment;

- lack of readiness for the digitalization of the independent learning process in preparing speech therapy students for inclusive activities;

- increasing requirements for the quality of training of speech therapy students in ensuring the speech and personal development of children in an inclusive educational environment and insufficient development of scientific and pedagogical support for this process.

When preparing speech therapy students for inclusive activities, their readiness for independent digitalization of the learning process is ensured if:

- The specific features of the preparation of speech therapy students for teaching activities in an inclusive educational environment are highlighted;

- an appropriate pedagogical model is developed as a systematic basis for this process;

- pedagogical conditions for the implementation of the pedagogical model are developed and implemented;

- to identify and substantiate the basic competencies necessary to prepare speech therapy students for inclusive activities and to implement them, to organize the practical component of the educational process through the organization of practice in an inclusive educational environment in order to prepare speech therapy students for inclusive activities, to strengthen all types of practices in an inclusive educational environment, and practical activities as tutors and assistants in educational organizations.

There have been many discussions in educational neurotechnology and robotics related to identifying the possibilities and limitations of digitizing the independent learning process in preparing speech therapy students for inclusive

activities . According to them:

1) Many researchers and teachers doubt the importance and necessity of the possibilities of digitizing the independent learning process in an inclusive educational environment, seeing the harmful psychological (cognitive, emotional, behavioral, value), social and physiological consequences of digital education, including “digital diseases”.

3) Some scientists believe that the neurotechnologies and robotics currently being developed are largely impractical, uncertain, ethically and scientifically weakly based, and therefore the boundaries of their use should be clearly defined. It is more effective if these considerations are not based on whether the use of digital tools is beneficial or harmful, but on where and when they can be effectively used. The availability and introduction of newly created technologies, programs and devices into education leads to a clear understanding by speech therapy students of what is happening and should happen as a result of the use of these developments.

Depending on the severity of the speech disorder, school-age children receive various types of speech therapy assistance. Children with mild speech disorders are admitted to public schools and can be treated in school speech therapy centers. The task of speech therapy centers is to correct disorders in the development of oral and written speech of students, to timely prevent and eliminate difficulties in mastering the general education program of students, to conduct educational work with teachers and parents on issues of speech disorders. In cases where speech disorders are obvious and cannot be corrected in a school speech therapy center, and when the child cannot work on an equal footing with peers due to the existing defect, teaching through digitalization activities gives a positive effect.

Inclusive education implies the implementation of a single curriculum for all categories of students with special educational needs, firstly, between primary and basic general education, and secondly, between special and general education programs. For children with difficulties in speech development, it is necessary to

provide optimal pedagogical conditions in accordance with their age and individual typological characteristics, somatic and neuropsychic health status. Within the framework of the educational process, there should be an interaction of diagnostics and consultation, correction and development, treatment and prevention, and social activities.

Conclusion. The digitalization of the independent learning process in preparing speech therapy students for inclusive activities should initially be limited to specific tasks to help teachers and students, which will not increase, but rather reduce, stress in education, making education more valuable and attractive. Although, being aware of artificial intelligence, people can share their own language, their own information systems, their own methods of solving problems, but it is difficult for them to become at least a subject of culture, a carrier of its instructions and prohibitions. Therefore, the digitalization of the independent learning process in preparing speech therapy students for inclusive activities makes the interaction of students and teachers interactive and effective, while increasing the quality of education, further individualizing the educational process.

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